

Hyper local delivery partner selection problem

Please rate the alternatives according to the sub criteria.

Name *

Monsur Rahaman

Designation *

Store operator

(A1) Dunzo

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Good

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e31 Customer Reviews & Ratings

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e32 Complaint Resolution Mechanism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e33 Consistency & Reliability

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e34 Product Handling & Condition

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e41 Rider Availability

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e52 App & Interface Usability

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

⌵ Dropdown

Medium ▼

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

⌵ Dropdown

Medium

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Good

(A2) Porter

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Medium ▼

e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e31 Customer Reviews & Ratings

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e32 Complaint Resolution Mechanism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium ▼

e33 Consistency & Reliability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e34 Product Handling & Condition

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e41 Rider Availability

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e52 App & Interface Usability

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

(A3) Borzo

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Medium ▼

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Medium ▼

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e31 Customer Reviews & Ratings

⌵ Dropdown

Medium ▼

e32 Complaint Resolution Mechanism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e33 Consistency & Reliability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e34 Product Handling & Condition

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e41 Rider Availability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

Dropdown

Medium ▼

e52 App & Interface Usability

Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

Dropdown

Medium ▼

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

Dropdown

Poor ▼

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

(A4) Shiprocket Quick

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e31 Customer Reviews & Ratings

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e32 Complaint Resolution Mechanism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e33 Consistency & Reliability

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e34 Product Handling & Condition

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e41 Rider Availability

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e52 App & Interface Usability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

Dropdown

Medium

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

Dropdown

Medium poor

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

Dropdown

Very Good

(A5) MOVER

e11 Delivery Speed

Dropdown

Medium poor

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

Dropdown

Poor

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

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⌵ Dropdown

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⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

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⌵ Dropdown

Medium ▼

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

Dropdown

Good

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

Dropdown

Poor

e52 App & Interface Usability

Dropdown

Poor

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

Dropdown

Poor

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

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e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

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Medium Good ▼

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

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Google Forms

Hyper local delivery partner selection problem

Please rate the alternatives according to the sub criteria.

Name *

Ritika Saha

Designation *

Quality control supervisor

(A1) Dunzo

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e31 Customer Reviews & Ratings

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e32 Complaint Resolution Mechanism

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e34 Product Handling & Condition

Dropdown

Good ▼

e41 Rider Availability

Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

Dropdown

Good ▼

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

⌵ Dropdown

Good

e52 App & Interface Usability

⌵ Dropdown

Good

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Poor

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

(A2) Porter

e11 Delivery Speed

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Good

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

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Good

e13 Scalability

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⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

(A3) Borzo

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

e31 Customer Reviews & Ratings

⌵ Dropdown

Medium ▼

e32 Complaint Resolution Mechanism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e33 Consistency & Reliability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e34 Product Handling & Condition

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e41 Rider Availability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium ▼

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e52 App & Interface Usability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

(A4) Shiprocket Quick

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

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e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

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Very Good ▼

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⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e34 Product Handling & Condition

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e41 Rider Availability

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e52 App & Interface Usability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

(A5) MOVER

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e31 Customer Reviews & Ratings

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e32 Complaint Resolution Mechanism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e33 Consistency & Reliability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e34 Product Handling & Condition

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e41 Rider Availability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

⌵ Dropdown

Poor

e52 App & Interface Usability

⌵ Dropdown

Poor

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

⌵ Dropdown

Good

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

⌵ Dropdown

Good

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Good

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Google.

Google Forms

Hyper local delivery partner selection problem

Please rate the alternatives according to the sub criteria.

Name *

Arindam Chatterjee

Designation *

Procurement Officer

(A1) Dunzo

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e31 Customer Reviews & Ratings

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e32 Complaint Resolution Mechanism

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e33 Consistency & Reliability

⌵ Dropdown

Good

e34 Product Handling & Condition

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good

e41 Rider Availability

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

⌵ Dropdown

Good

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e52 App & Interface Usability

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

⌵ Dropdown

Medium ▼

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

(A2) Porter

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Poor

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Medium

e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

e31 Customer Reviews & Ratings

⌵ Dropdown

Good

e32 Complaint Resolution Mechanism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

e33 Consistency & Reliability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e34 Product Handling & Condition

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e41 Rider Availability

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e52 App & Interface Usability

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

(A3) Borzo

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Medium ▼

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e31 Customer Reviews & Ratings

⌵ Dropdown

Medium ▼

e32 Complaint Resolution Mechanism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e33 Consistency & Reliability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e34 Product Handling & Condition

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e41 Rider Availability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium ▼

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium ▼

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

⌵ Dropdown

Medium

e52 App & Interface Usability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

⌵ Dropdown

Medium

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

⌵ Dropdown

Poor

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

(A4) Shiprocket Quick

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Good

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Good

e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good

e31 Customer Reviews & Ratings

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

e32 Complaint Resolution Mechanism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

e33 Consistency & Reliability

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e34 Product Handling & Condition

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e41 Rider Availability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e52 App & Interface Usability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

(A5) MOVER

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

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Medium poor ▼

e41 Rider Availability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e52 App & Interface Usability

Dropdown

Poor ▼

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Poor ▼

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

Dropdown

Good ▼

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Good

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Google.

Google Forms

Hyper local delivery partner selection problem

Please rate the alternatives according to the sub criteria.

Name *

Moumita Ghosh

Designation *

Logistics Coordinator

(A1) Dunzo

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Good

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

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Medium poor ▼

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Good

e52 App & Interface Usability

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Very Good

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

⌵ Dropdown

Medium

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

(A2) Porter

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Poor

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor

e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

e31 Customer Reviews & Ratings

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

e32 Complaint Resolution Mechanism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

e33 Consistency & Reliability

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⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

(A3) Borzo

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e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

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⌵ Dropdown

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e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

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e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good

e31 Customer Reviews & Ratings

⌵ Dropdown

Good

e32 Complaint Resolution Mechanism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

e33 Consistency & Reliability

⌵ Dropdown

Good

e34 Product Handling & Condition

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good

e41 Rider Availability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e52 App & Interface Usability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

(A5) MOVER

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e31 Customer Reviews & Ratings

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e32 Complaint Resolution Mechanism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e33 Consistency & Reliability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium ▼

e34 Product Handling & Condition

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e41 Rider Availability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e52 App & Interface Usability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Good

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Good

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Google Forms

Hyper local delivery partner selection problem

Please rate the alternatives according to the sub criteria.

Name *

Subhajit Banerjee

Designation *

Supply Chain Analytics Executive

(A1) Dunzo

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e31 Customer Reviews & Ratings

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e32 Complaint Resolution Mechanism

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e33 Consistency & Reliability

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e34 Product Handling & Condition

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e41 Rider Availability

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

⌵ Dropdown

Good

e52 App & Interface Usability

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

⌵ Dropdown

Good

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

⌵ Dropdown

Medium

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Medium ▼

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

(A2) Porter

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Poor

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Medium

e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

e31 Customer Reviews & Ratings

⌵ Dropdown

Good

e32 Complaint Resolution Mechanism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

e33 Consistency & Reliability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e34 Product Handling & Condition

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e41 Rider Availability

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e52 App & Interface Usability

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

(A3) Borzo

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Medium ▼

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e31 Customer Reviews & Ratings

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e32 Complaint Resolution Mechanism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e33 Consistency & Reliability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e34 Product Handling & Condition

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e41 Rider Availability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e52 App & Interface Usability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

⌵ Dropdown

Medium ▼

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

(A4) Shiprocket Quick

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e31 Customer Reviews & Ratings

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e32 Complaint Resolution Mechanism

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e33 Consistency & Reliability

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e34 Product Handling & Condition

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e41 Rider Availability

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e52 App & Interface Usability

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

(A5) MOVER

e11 Delivery Speed

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e12 Order Fulfillment Rate

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e13 Scalability

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

e21 Commission Fees

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e22 Subscription/Partnership Costs

⌵ Dropdown

Very Good ▼

e23 Cash on Delivery (COD) Handling

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e31 Customer Reviews & Ratings

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e32 Complaint Resolution Mechanism

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

e33 Consistency & Reliability

Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e34 Product Handling & Condition

Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e41 Rider Availability

Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e42 Rider Behavior & Professionalism

Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e43 Incentive Structure for Riders

Dropdown

Good ▼

e51 Real-time Order Tracking

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e52 App & Interface Usability

⌵ Dropdown

Poor ▼

e53 AI & Predictive Analytics

⌵ Dropdown

Medium poor ▼

e61 Eco-friendly Packaging & Delivery Practices

⌵ Dropdown

Good ▼

e62 Rider Well-being & Fair Wages

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good ▼

e63 Carbon Footprint Reduction Measures

⌵ Dropdown

Good

e64 Partnerships with Local Vendors

⌵ Dropdown

Medium Good

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